

AVIONICS INTERFERENCE FROM PORTABLE ELECTRONIC DEVICES: REVIEW OF THE AVIATION SAFETY REPORTING SYSTEM DATABASE

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Abstract

The Aviation Safety Reporting System (ASRS) database was reviewed for incident reports involving interference to avionics from portable electronic devices (PEDs). There were 125 incident reports identified. Examination of these reports revealed a wide variety of affected avionics, predominately navigation. A diverse group of passenger electronics is mentioned, primarily cellular phones and laptop computers. Relationships between categories of PEDs and avionics were shown to exist statistically. Many aircraft models were involved in the incidents, but preliminary analysis showed that no specific model was more vulnerable than any other. There were safety critical avionics involved and events occurred at critical flight phases. Some incident reports clearly demonstrated the potential for catastrophe. This paper, the first published review of the ASRS data in close to a decade, serves as a reminder that attention to this topic is important and timely due to technology advances, proliferation of consumer electronic devices and aging aircraft.

Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to provide a review of the ASRS incident reports involving PED interference to avionics and to suggest what these data might be demonstrating. This paper contains qualitative and quantitative analyses. The usefulness of an incident database as a qualitative tool has been generally accepted. Sheryl Chappell, former ASRS scientist, states that, "Incident data are ideally suited for proving the existence of a safety issue, understanding its possible causes, defining potential interventions..." [1]. Its acceptance as a quantitative tool has been less enthusiastic. Chappell points out that caution is required in quantitative analysis of incident data.

This paper contains five sections. The first provides a description of the ASRS, its usefulness, and limitations. The second explains how the data for this paper were obtained and categorized. The third provides summaries of the incident reports and an estimate for the reporting rate. The fourth reports whether specific combinations of avionics and PEDs demonstrated relationships. The fifth section presents narratives taken from the incident reports that highlight the potential consequences.

Aviation Safety Reporting System

The ASRS is a voluntary, confidential, and non-punitive system operated by NASA that allows flight crews, air traffic controllers, maintenance personnel and others to submit reports involving safety incidents. The reports are sanitized and summarized by a staff of experienced pilots and air traffic controllers in a form that assures confidentiality. Conditional immunity is granted to those who file reports. Analysts can search the database either by making a search request to NASA or by performing a search through the FAA's Office of System Safety's web page.¹

The ASRS has received more than 500,000 incident reports, issued more than 4,000 safety alerts and identified approximately 60 reports and papers that have drawn upon the database. In testimony last year before the House, Linda Connell, ASRS Director, enumerated the many ways it has been used to address real aviation safety issues [2]. The ASRS is an important aviation safety tool. It has become a cornerstone of aviation safety, and a model for other fields, such as medicine [3].

There are several sources of bias in the ASRS data. The influence of both reporters and users of incident data has been documented [1]. Reporter

¹ www.nasdac.faa.gov

bias can arise from media coverage, employment status, or the seriousness of the incident. Researcher (end user) bias can be introduced through improper coding or recording of data.

The processing of data by ASRS staff also creates bias. The ASRS staff chooses entries to the database on the basis of a "watch list." Certain incidents are considered critical and are automatically entered. These incidents typically predominate. The staff then exercises their judgment in choosing other entries. Their focus shifts over time as different kinds of events command attention. About 20-25% of the reports that are submitted to the ASRS are entered into the database. Between 1995 and 2001, 10% of the submitted reports were randomly selected and this was about half of all the entries being made. This practice has since been discontinued due to budget cuts. Since only a portion of the incident reports received by ASRS are entered into the database and reviewers have considerable leeway on selection criteria, bias is a concern.

The ability to address the voluntary and confidential nature of incident reports with large numbers of similar accounts and to deal with reporting bias through correlation techniques has been stated [1]. And, the random entries made between 1995 and 2001 can overcome the staff processing bias. However, care is required. This paper has used caution in developing its findings and the reader is urged to consider the data limitations before application.

Previous Research Using ASRS

The last published database analysis of suspected interference to avionics by PEDs was issued by the Radio Technical Commission for Aeronautics (RTCA) in 1996 [4]. That report, RTCA DO-233, was in response to a 1992 House Transportation Appropriations Bill [5] that requested a determination of the potential for interference to aircraft systems from carry-on PEDs. The data in RTCA DO-233 covered the period from 1982 to 1993. It identified 34 incidents in the ASRS database and another 103 incidents from other sources.² The report was hesitant to

² International Air Transport Association (IATA) and reports direct to the RTCA Special Committees 156 and 177.

accept these database entries as strong evidence of a problem:

Most of the reports contain very few details of correlation confirmation, but there were several cases where the PED was turned off and on again and a definite correlation was indicated.

The RTCA DO-233 report remains the basis for existing airline policies and regulations in this area.

The Data

The data used in this report are the result of ASRS database searches performed over the period April – June 2002 using the FAA's Office of System Safety's web page. The available data were current through March 2001.

Searches

Initial queries to the database revealed that searching on broad terms such as "portable electronic device" or "PED" was insufficient to identify all PED-related reports of interference. To overcome this, an exhaustive list of terms that covered most commercial electronic devices was developed. The search strategy was impractical for certain terms like "computer," that produced over 2,500 hits. Initial review of these reports showed that very few of these involved interference to avionics. Thus, refinements were made to identify the target reports using Boolean operators. A search of "computer" and "interference" yields only 24 responses. Other refinements included accounting for misspellings and searching for the affected systems (autopilot, VOR, etc.). A sample of the search strategies is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample Search Strategies

cell phone
cellular
cellular AND phone
gameboy
game AND boy
DVD
laptop AND interference
medical AND device
VOR AND interference
VOR AND laptop

Table 2. Evidence Level Definitions

Level	Description
5	The affected aircraft system returned to normal operation after termination of PED operation and subsequently demonstrated anomalous activity when the suspected PED was operated again.
4	The interference corrected soon after a pilot or flight attendant announcement was made requesting that electronic devices be turned off. There was confirmation that the passengers complied with the request.
3	The interference corrected soon after a pilot or flight attendant announcement was made requesting that electronic devices be turned off. There was no confirmation that passengers complied with the request.
2	A PED was known to be on the aircraft and there were indications that it was in use at some point during the flight, but no check was performed to correlate to the interference.
1	It is unknown if a PED was in use or on the aircraft at the time of the anomaly

The pertinent information from each report was recorded: report number, date of occurrence, affected avionics, suspected PED(s), aircraft model, and flight phase. A determination of the avionics affected and the PED(s) causing the interference were made after reading the report narrative.³ The report narratives sometimes were vague and only relayed suspicions of an interference event or what caused it. However, many reports provided sufficient evidence and detail that it was likely that an identified device(s) did cause or contribute to an anomaly. It is possible that some of the identified PEDs did not contribute to the interference even though they were identified as the “sources.”

A coding instrument was developed to capture the degree to which the narrative supported a finding of interference. The coding scheme is similar to the “level of correlation” used in the RTCA DO-233 report. The “evidence” level, as defined in Table 2, was assigned after considering the report author’s event description. The researcher did not attempt to second-guess the report author, but rather tried to interpret the narrative presentation. The evidence level does not imply independent verification of the event or that any subsequent evaluation produced support for the reporter’s conclusion. Loosely speaking a high evidence level identifies those reports that likely were interference events and correctly identified the avionics and PEDs involved.

³ Based on the researcher’s experience in consultation with Jay Apt, a pilot and former NASA Scientist/Astronaut.

Concern over the accuracy of these reports has been raised. However, the reporting of a large number of similar incidents over an extended period of time reduces the likelihood of erroneous associations [1].

Incident Summaries

The purpose of this section is to provide a summarization of the incident reports describing interference to avionics from PEDs. In this section all reports were used regardless of their assigned

Figure 1. Interference To Avionics From PEDs: ASRS Entries By Year

evidence level. The database search revealed 125 incidents. The incident entries by year are presented in Figure 1.

The number of entries should not be considered the number of occurrences. First, it is not known if all reported incidents are entered into the database. Second, some of the reported incidents may not be interference events (i.e. false

positives). Third, and most important the amount of underreporting is not known. Underreporting can be influenced by reports being filed elsewhere, the event not being recognized as interference (false negative), or the flight crew not attaching significance to the event.

The limitations aside, the following observations are made:

1. The peak entries come in 1993 and 1994. This coincides with the Congressional interest that prompted RTCA DO-233.
2. Entries decline over the next few years. This occurs after airlines begin adopting policies that require passenger electronics to be turned off below 10,000 ft.
3. After 1996, the trend is increasing. This is possibly due to the increasing number of flights, consumer electronics proliferation, aging aircraft systems, and/or passenger non-compliance with airline policies.

There were 57 incidents where the evidence level was 4 or 5 and 77 incidents where the evidence level was at least 3.

The aircraft involved in the 125 incidents were all commercial aircraft operating under Federal Aviation Regulation (FAR) Part 121 or 135 except for one helicopter operating under FAR Part 91.

Reporting Rates

The reports submitted to ASRS that are not selected for entry into the database are destroyed. Thus, establishing the number of PED interference reports filed is left to estimation. Due to the infrequent nature of these types of reports NASA claims to enter "most" [6]. However, no formal records are available to demonstrate this.

The random sample incident reports filed between 1995 and 2001 were used to establish a yearly average ($\mu = 1.5$, $\sigma = 1.05$). The actual mean is between 0.66 and 2.34 using a 95% confidence interval. This implies that the actual yearly reporting rate could be as high as 23.

Additionally, events likely go unreported. This means that PED interference events could be occurring a few times each month. Given that hazardous incidents have been shown to lead to accidents [7] these numbers are too large to ignore.

What Avionics Were Affected?

The most frequently cited systems involve navigation. The VOR⁴ was the most cited system. The VOR incidents tended to be easily noticed by the flight crew and non-critical in nature. However, a few created hazardous situations.⁵ Also, many incidents involved critical systems. Instrument landing systems (ILS) were affected 17 times, autopilot systems were affected 8 times and an engine fuel controller was affected once. The potential for serious consequence is markedly increased when such critical systems are affected. The affected systems are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Avionics Associated With Incidents

Aircraft System	Occurrences
VOR	47
Navigation *	33
Instrument Landing System	17
Communication Radio	12
Radar Altimeter	10
Autopilot	8
GPWS	7
TCASII	4
Compass	4
Flight Display	3
Caution/Advisory Light	2
Gyro	1
Engine Fuel controller	1

* Navigation other than VOR

What PEDs Are Causing The Interference?

The PEDs most often cited as being potential offending sources of interference were cellular phones and laptop computers. They accounted for almost 60% of the incidents. Electronic games, AM/FM radios, CD/DVD players, and pagers were also frequently cited. Medical electronic devices were mentioned only twice; however new medical electronics (such as insulin pumps) may become an issue. A list of cited PEDs is provided in Table 4.

⁴ The VHF Omni-Range (VOR) is the basic electronic navigation system in use today and operates in the frequency band from 108.0 to 117.95 MHz.

⁵ ASRS Report 226306 described a missed approach and ASRS Report 440557 a potential conflict with another aircraft.

Table 4. PEDs Associated With Incidents

PED	Occurrences
Cellular phone	41
Laptop computer	34
Electronic game	15
AM/FM radio *	12
CD/DVD player	7
Pager	6
Camera/video	3
Portable TV	3
Transmitter	3
Heart monitor	1
Electronic device	1
Calculator	1
Hearing aid	1
PDA	1
Unknown	23

* AM/FM radio includes cassette players

While any effort to characterize PED emission profiles or their potential to interfere with avionics is encouraged, analytic resources are limited. The starting point is to concentrate efforts on cellular phones and laptop computers. Further support for this assertion is that they are among the most utilized consumer portable electronics. The influence of age on laptops may be particularly interesting. Finally, given the rapidly changing electronics market attention should also be paid to emerging technologies and devices, such as ultrawideband (UWB) and 802.11.

Which PED-Avionics Combinations Occurred The Most?

The most cited combination of PED-avionics interference was cellular phones affecting VOR navigation systems, 20 incidents. Laptop computers affecting VOR systems were also prevalent, cited 15 times. The most common combinations are shown in Table 5. Cellular phones and laptop computers were involved in the 4 most frequent combinations. They were also involved in 6 of the 8 most frequent combinations.

This again points to concentrating efforts on the evaluation of cellular phones and laptop computers.

Table 5. PED-Avionics Combinations Associated With Incidents

PED-Avionics Combination	Occurrences
Cellular phone-VOR	20
Laptop-VOR	15
Cellular phone-navigation	9
Laptop-navigation	9
Electronic game-VOR	8
Cellular phone-ILS	6
Cell phone – aircraft radio	6
AM/FM radio-VOR	6
AM/FM radio-navigation	5

* Navigation is other than VOR

** AM/FM radio includes cassette players

When Does The Interference Occur?

While the majority of incidents occurred during the cruise portion of flight, close to half occurred within the “sterile” cockpit window.⁶ Incidents that occur during these phases of flight are more critical and their importance cannot be overstated. These results indicate that passengers may not be complying with the airline requirements that all electronics be turned off and stowed during critical phases of flight. This is supported by incident reports to the ASRS, a small mail-survey of passengers conducted last year [8], and informal reports from colleagues. The breakdown of flight phase for avionics interference events from PEDs is shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Flight Phase Associated With Incidents

Flight Phase	Occurrences
Pre-flight	4
Departure	25
Cruise	62
Approach	34

* Departure includes takeoff and climb

** Approach includes descent and landing

What Aircraft Models Are Affected?

Given the nature of the data used for this evaluation it would be unfair to make any authoritative statement about the aircraft models or

⁶ The “sterile” cockpit prohibits crew members from performing non-essential duties when the aircraft is involved in taxi, takeoff, landing and all other operations conducted below 10,000 ft MSL due to the criticality of flight [FAR 121.542] and [FAR 135.100].

manufacturers involved in the anomalies. However, a few findings seem to be fair and noteworthy.

First, many aircraft models and manufacturers were found to be involved. Overall, there were 13 different aircraft models and 7 manufacturers found to be involved. The actual number of models and manufacturers may be higher, but prior to 1994 only a general aircraft description was given in the incident reports.⁷ The characteristics of the aircraft models involved were varied: large, medium and small transport; jet and turbo propeller; “fly-by-wire,” etc.

Second, initial analysis did not show any particular aircraft model or manufacturer to be involved in a disproportionately large number of incidents. This analysis was not finalized in time for this paper and will be reported on subsequently if initial assessments are incorrect. The influence of reporting bias may be significant in this analysis. For example, a particular airline may use mostly one model of aircraft and they also may encourage their pilots to report incidents. This could act to erroneously mask the percentage of incidents associated with an aircraft model or manufacturer.

The involvement of many aircraft models and manufacturers seems suggestive that the problem needs to be addressed at an industry level. Government support in the form of both financial and engineering support seems appropriate given the public safety implications and the current industry economic situation.

Correlations

The following section relays information about the correlation between passenger electronics and aircraft systems associated with the incidents. These correlations do not necessarily imply causation. Nor does a lack of correlation disqualify the existence of relationships. This section is mainly provided as information to researchers to help refine their activities.

To obtain a clear picture of what relationships might exist, the data were grouped and evaluated at various evidence levels. They are referred to as high evidence data (levels 4 and 5), intermediate evidence data (levels 3, 4 and 5), and low evidence

data (all levels). Correlation was performed between the aircraft systems described in Table 3 and the passenger electronics described in Table 4. The Pearson correlation values described below are not very high. However, the level of significance may be more important for this application as it involves a large number of parameter correlations.

Cell Phones Vs. ILS

The correlation between cellular phones and instrument landing system (ILS) anomalies showed a weak significance for high evidence data, $r = 0.2025$ with $p = 0.1873$ using Fisher’s Exact Test. The correlation was less significant when using lower evidence data sets. However, the correlation between unknown sources and ILS anomalies was significant for intermediate evidence data, $r = 0.5286$, $p < 0.0001$ and low evidence data, $r = 0.3537$, $p < 0.0001$. It is theorized that many of these unknown sources are cell phones. This is derived from the following:

1. Passengers are more likely to initiate calls during approach due to aircraft proximity to the ground (i.e. cellular base stations) and the desire to inform friends, relatives, or colleagues of their impending arrival.
2. A higher percentage of approach phase incidents are observed for the low evidence levels (1, 2 and 3).
3. Flight crews are busy during landing and might not have time to determine which PEDs are in use.

Thus, cellular phones interfering with ILS intuitively makes sense and is supported by the data.

Electronic Games Vs. VOR

The correlation between electronic games and VOR anomalies was significant for high evidence data, $r = 0.3485$ with $p = 0.0204$ using Fisher’s Exact Test. The correlation was less significant for intermediate and low evidence data.

Electronic games operate at relatively low clock speeds that are close to the VOR operating frequency range. Game electronics are very likely to be dropped, thrown, or beaten by their child owners and this can render electromagnetic

⁷ For example: large transport, low wing, 3 turbojet engines

emission control measures ineffective. Thus, this finding seems to be worth further exploration.

CD/DVD Players Vs. Radio Communications

The correlation between CD and DVD players and aircraft radio communication system anomalies was significant for high evidence data, $r = 0.3157$ with $p = 0.0696$ using Fisher's Exact Test. The correlation was less significant for intermediate and low evidence data.

There is no immediate insight as to why this relationship may exist, but it is offered for informational purposes. The large number of correlations performed creates an expectation that by chance a few relationships will appear significant and this could be the case here.

Beyond Numbers: The Narratives

The following narrative excerpts demonstrate how interference creates hazardous situations that can become incidents or accidents.

A crew who had lost their electronic flight instrument system (EFIS) stated:

While in this event no serious harm was done, the effect could have been different if the aircraft was in heavy weather flying a complicated departure or arrival.⁸

After being unaware he was off course a pilot stated, "[I] would have really been sweating if it had been instrument flight rules in that mountain area."⁹ Another crew reported, "abruptly, the airplane entered a 30 degree bank."¹⁰ If that occurred during takeoff, landing, a high workload period or in bad weather the consequences could be catastrophic. Finally, one pilot reported:

We were advised by air traffic control that our course was 7 mi off the center course...A possible contributing factor was caused by poor human performance reaction, due to extended scheduled long duty days prior to this flight.¹¹

⁸ ASRS Report 236534.

⁹ ASRS Report 337254.

¹⁰ ASRS Report 277118.

¹¹ ASRS Report 255695.

The subtle nature of interference incidents can be such that flight crews may not react immediately or at all. This can create extreme hazards such as in the case of course deviations.

Summary

The following provides a summary of the key findings in this report:

1. There were 125 entries in the ASRS database that involved suspected interference to avionics from passenger electronics. Given that all reports filed are not entered into the database and that underreporting is likely the topic cannot be ignored.
2. The reporting rate of incidents to the ASRS may be a few times each month and the occurrence rate is likely higher.
3. Critical aircraft systems have been reported as affected in these incidents.
4. Incidents were reported as occurring at critical flight phases (i.e. approach and landing).
5. Many aircraft models and manufacturers were involved in the incidents. This suggests that the problem needs to be addressed at an industry level.
6. Certain passenger electronics were shown to be correlated to aircraft systems and may be good starting points for more aggressive evaluation.
7. The report narratives provide evidence of the hazards created by these incidents and highlight the potential for catastrophe.
8. Government assistance is warranted in the interest of public safety and given the current economic state of the airline industry.

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Suggested Reading

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